

Sample Permission / Ethical Compliance Letter

To Whom It May Concern,

This letter is to certify that the study entitled “*Sustainable Water Treatment: Acid-Induced Biopolymers from Bagasse as Natural Coagulants for Turbidity Reduction*” conducted by Dr. Anuwat Aunkham and the research team under the Program of Environmental Health, School of Health Science, Mae Fah Luang University, Chiang Rai, Thailand, was performed in compliance with institutional and local regulations.

The raw materials used in this study consisted of sugarcane bagasse derived from *Saccharum officinarum L.* The bagasse was obtained from local sugarcane juice vendors at Mae Fah Luang University Market, located at 333 Moo 1, Tha Sut Subdistrict, Mueang District, Chiang Rai Province, Thailand. The collected bagasse was an agricultural by-product remaining after sugarcane juice extraction and would otherwise have been discarded as waste.

Raw water samples used in this study were collected from the Kok River at Rim Kok, Mueang Chiang Rai District, Chiang Rai 57100, Thailand (19.924858, 99.864499). The sampling location is a publicly accessible natural water resource that can be freely accessed and utilized by the general public in Thailand. Therefore, no special permission or authorization from governmental or local agencies was required for water sample collection conducted for experimental and analytical purposes.

The collection and use of these non-living materials did not involve endangered or protected species and did not require specific environmental or ethical permits under Thai law. All procedures were conducted in accordance with standard environmental sampling practices and the research guidelines of Mae Fah Luang University.

Therefore, no specific permits were required for this work.

Sincerely,

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